

DIC Analysis of Shrinkage Behaviors of Dental Composites During Dental Restoration

J.H. Park¹, N.S. Choi^{2*}

¹ Department of Mech. Eng., Hanyang Univ., Seongdong-gu, Seoul, Korea

² Department of Mech. Eng., Hanyang Univ., Ansan, Gyeonggi-do, Korea

* Corresponding author (nschoi@hanyang.ac.kr)

Introduction

- ❖ Polymerization shrinkage during dental restoration

- Polymerization shrinkage
- Debonding
- Contraction stress
- Crack, defect... 2nd caries
- Reduction of oral-age

- ❖ Digital image correlation

Experimental

- ❖ Resins and specimen preparation

Composite	Resin matrix	Filler	Polymerization shrinkage (vol %)
Clearfil AP-X (Kuraray)	Bis-GMA TEGDMA	3 μ m Barium glass, Silica particle (85.5 wt%)	1.9 ¹⁾
Filtek P90 (3M ESPE)	Silorane	0.01-3.5 μ m (average 0.47 μ m) quartz particles, yttrium fluoride (76 wt%)	0.88 ²⁾

- ❖ Camera measurement for DIC

DIC measurement condition		
	During irradiation	After irradiation
Frame rate	3 f/s	10 f/s
Exposed time	0.2 ms	300 ms
Recorded time	20 s	580 s

Results & discussion

- ❖ Principal strain distributions of (a) AP-X and (b) P90 by DIC measurement

- ❖ Radial shrinkage strain behaviors of AP-X during and after LED irradiation

- ❖ Radial shrinkage strain behaviors of P90 during and after LED irradiation

Conclusion

- The measured results by DIC method showed that the radial shrinkage strains rapidly increased for the irradiation period, but showed a different shrinkage speed at the respective radii, and converged to a constant value after irradiation stop. Also, the radial shrinkage strain of the resin part was the maximum near the center of the specimen, and happened to be -0.56% for Clearfil AP-X and -0.44% for Filtek P90.